

Knowledge, Attitude and practice of breast self-examination among undergraduate female medical students in KIMS, Amalapuram

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ABSTRACT

Background: Breast self-examination is an important screening tool for early identification of breast carcinoma. Its knowledge and correct practice methods are important for better results. This study aims to evaluate and compare the knowledge, attitude and practice of Breast self-examination among phase 1, phase 2 and phase 3 MBBS students.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 159 MBBS students of the Phase I, phase II and Phase III part I students in Konaseema institute of medical sciences & RF, Amalapuram. Google Forms was used to collect study data using a pre-designed, semi-structured questionnaire. For statistical analysis, SPSS software version 2020 was utilized.

Results: Out of the 159 study participants, 33.3% are from phase-1 MBBS, 35.2% and 31.4% are from phase II and Phase III part 1 respectively. Majority of the participants i.e. 96.2% agreed that BSE is effective for early identification of breast carcinoma and all the women should know the correct procedure of BSE for early detection (95.6%). 84.9% were aware that BSE and mammography are recommended screening methods for breast cancer. In present study, 7(4.4%) participants had identified some abnormalities during BSE. First Year Knowledge and Second Year Knowledge have a substantial positive connection ($r = .368$, $p = .008$), indicating that second-year students knew more about BSE than first-year students did.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the study shows strong awareness of BSE among participants, with most recognizing its role in early breast cancer detection. 4.4% identified abnormalities during BSE, highlighting the need for further education and practical training. These findings emphasize

the importance of integrating breast cancer awareness and screening education into the medical curriculum.

Key words: Breast self-examination, Knowledge of BSE, health education, Undergraduate female healthcare students, Breast cancer awareness

Introduction:

Breast carcinoma is the second leading cause of cancer death among women overall, after lung cancer⁽¹⁾. Epidemiological studies have shown that the global burden of breast carcinoma is expected to cross almost 2 million by the year 2030⁽²⁾. In India, it accounts for the second most common cancer in women. Around 80,000 cases are estimated to occur annually. The age-standardized incidence rate of breast cancer among Indian women is 22.9 and the mortality rate is 11.19.⁽³⁾

Breast cancer in women aged less than 35 years is uncommon and accounts for 1%-2% of all breast cancers worldwide⁽⁴⁾. Recent years has noted a trend of increasing incidence of young breast cancer in India⁽⁵⁾

The incidence of breast cancer in young Indian women is seen to be associated with aggressive histology and loss of estrogen and progesterone receptor expression⁽⁶⁾. Breast cancer in young women has significant implications on quality of life, poses major challenges in detection, treatment, and is associated with relatively poorer out- come.⁽⁷⁾

The three screening methods currently recommended by the American Cancer Society (2010) for early detection of breast cancer are clinical breast examination (CBE), mammography, and breast self-examination⁽⁸⁾. CBE and mammography require hospital visit and specialized equipment and expertise whereas BSE is an inexpensive tool that can be carried out by women themselves⁽⁹⁾.

Breast self-examination is a simple, very low cost, non-invasive with no special material/tool requirements and it is an effective diagnostic method for breast cancer which only takes five minutes to apply⁽¹⁰⁾.

Methodology:

Study Design: A cross-sectional study was conducted.

Study Population and Study Site: The study was conducted among female Phase 1, Phase 2, and Phase 3 MBBS students at Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences, Amalapuram, Andhra Pradesh, India, to assess their knowledge, attitude, and practice of Breast Self-Examination (BSE).

Study Duration: The study was carried out from 01/12/2024 to 01/02/2025.

Sample Technique: Convenient sampling was used.

Inclusion Criteria: Female Phase 1, Phase 2, and Phase 3 MBBS students of Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences, who were present at the time of data collection and aged above 15 years and below 30 years, were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Female Phase 1, Phase 2, and Phase 3 MBBS students who were not willing to participate were excluded.

Ethical Considerations: Institutional ethics committee approval was obtained, and informed consent was taken from all participants.

Data Collection: Data was collected using a pre-tested and pre-structured questionnaire. Google Forms were sent to all students, and they were asked to complete the forms.

Data Analysis and Interpretation: The data was entered into a Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheet. Summarization and analysis of the data were carried out using IBM SPSS Software version 20 (licensed). Descriptive statistics, including frequency and percentage, were used, and inferential statistics, specifically the Chi-square test, were applied.

Results

Table: -1 Demographic details of study participants

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Age		
17 - 18 years	29	18.2
19 - 22 years	130	81.8
Year of study		
1 st year	53	33.3
2 nd year	56	35.2
3 rd year	50	31.4
Family history of breast carcinoma		
Yes	12	7.5
No	147	92.5
Source of knowledge about BSE		
Internet / social media	26	16.4
Family / Friends	14	8.8
Education	119	74.8
Total	159	100

Out of the 159 study participants, 33.3% are from phase-1 MBBS, 35.2% and 31.4% are from phase II and Phase III part 1 respectively. Majority of students are between 19-22 years of age i.e. 81.8%. 12(7.5%) of the students said that having a family history of breast cancer. The most of the participants, 119 (74.8%), reported that their source of knowledge about breast self-examination (BSE) came from education. Followed by 26 (16.4%) and 14(8.8%) from Internet or social media and Family / Friends respectively.

Table: -2

**Knowledge Regarding Breast Self-Examination (BSE) Among study
Participants**

Knowledge regarding Breast Self Examination	YES	NO	I DON' T KNOW
1) Breast Self Examination is an effective tool for early identification of breast carcinoma	153 (96.2)	0	6 (3.8)
2) Breast Self Examination should be done at monthly frequency by all the women	135 (84.9)	0	24 (15.1)
3) Breast Self Examination is performed by using pads of middle three fingers in a methodical way in circular motions	96 (60.4)	3 (1.9)	60 (37.7)
4) Examination of both axilla is a part of Breast Self Examination	133 (83.6)	2 (1.3)	24 (15.1)
5) Visual examination of shape and size of breast is an important step in Breast Self Examination	127 (79.9)	7 (4.4)	25 (15.7)
6) Breast Self Examination also includes squeezing the nipple to look for any discharge	116 (73)	7 (4.4)	36 (22.6)
7) Identification of any lump or abnormality in breast during Breast Self Examination warrants immediate clinical examination by health care professional	147 (92.5)	1 (0.6)	11 (6.9)
8) Dimpling, puckering of skin over breast and Nipple discharge are worrisome features	120 (75.5)	1 (0.6)	38 (23.9)
9) Early-menarche and late-menopause are risk factors for breast carcinoma.	80 (50.3)	21 (13.2)	58 (36.5)
10) Retraction or inversion of nipple is a sign of breast carcinoma	91 (57.2)	7 (4.4)	61 (38.4)
11) Lump in breast always need not be cancer	12 (78)	14 (8.8)	21 (13.2)
12) BSE and mammogram are recommended screening methods for carcinoma breast	135 (84.9)	2 (1.3)	22 (13.8)

A majority of participants, i.e. 96.2% agreed that BSE is effective for early identification of breast carcinoma. And 84.9% were aware that BSE should be done monthly. Only 60.4% knew that BSE is performed using the pads of the middle three fingers in circular motions and 37.7% participants don't know how to perform. 83.6% correctly identified that the axilla (armpits) must be examined as part of BSE. 73% knew that squeezing the nipple to check for discharge is part of BSE, while 22.6% were unsure. 75.5% identified dimpling, puckering of skin, and nipple discharge as worrisome signs.

Only 57.2% knew that nipple retraction/inversion is a sign of breast carcinoma. Only 50.3% knew that early menarche and late menopause are risk factors, while 36.5% were unsure, and 13.2% disagreed. 92.5% agreed that any abnormality found during BSE warrants immediate clinical examination. **78%** knew that not all breast lumps are cancerous. A majority of the participants were aware that BSE and mammography are recommended screening methods for breast cancer 135 (84.9).

Table-3

Participants attitudes toward Breast Self-Examination (BSE)

Attitude	Frequency	Percent
1.It is embarrassing to do Breast Self Examination		
Strongly disagree	78	49.1
Disagree	54	34.0
Neutral	22	13.8
Agree	3	1.9
Strongly agree	2	1.3
2.It is uncomfortable to discuss about Breast Self Examination with friends and family		
Strongly disagree	49	30.8
Disagree	57	35.8
Neutral	35	22.0
Agree	16	10.1

Strongly agree	2	1.3
3.Breast Self Examination is waste of time		
Strongly disagree	124	78.0
Disagree	33	20.8
Neutral	2	1.3
Agree	0	0
Strongly agree	0	0
4.There is no need for women to perform Breast Self Examination		
Strongly disagree	113	71.1
Disagree	40	25.2
Neutral	2	1.3
Agree	3	1.9
Strongly agree	1	.6
5.I am afraid to do Breast Self Examination		
Strongly disagree	58	36.5
Disagree	63	39.6
Neutral	26	16.4
Agree	11	6.9
Strongly agree	1	.6
6.Interested in doing Breast Self Examination as I care about my health		
Strongly disagree	1	.6
Disagree	4	2.5
Neutral	20	12.6
Agree	72	45.3
Strongly agree	62	39.0
7.Avoid Breast Self Examination because I worry, I might find some abnormality		
Strongly disagree	65	40.9
Disagree	61	38.4
Neutral	18	11.3
Agree	12	7.5

Strongly agree	3	1.9
8.It is important for all the women to know correct procedure of Breast Self Examination		
Strongly disagree	2	1.3
Disagree	0	0
Neutral	5	3.1
Agree	43	27.0
Strongly agree	109	68.6
Total	159	100.0

The majority (83.1%) of students disagreed/strongly disagreed with the statement that BSE is embarrassing to perform. Only a small percentage (3.2%) agreed or strongly agreed with the embarrassment associated with BSE. Most students (66.6%) disagreed or strongly disagreed with the idea that it is uncomfortable to discuss BSE with family or friends. A smaller group (11.4%) agree or strongly agree with the discomfort in discussing BSE. 124 (78.0%) of participants rejecting the idea that BSE is unhelpful or ineffective. A smaller group were disagreed (20.8%), and only 1.3% were neutral. 113(71.1%), strongly disagreed to no need for women to perform Breast Self-Examination.

Only a small percentage agree 3(1.9%,) or are neutral 2(1.3%). A majority (76.1%) either disagreed (39.6%) or strongly disagreed (36.5%) with that they are afraid to perform a BSE, indicating that fear is not a significant barrier. Most respondents agree (45.3%) or strongly agree (39.0%) with the statement that they are interested in doing a BSE. Majority (79.3%) of respondents strongly disagreed or disagreed with the idea of avoiding BSE due to worry about finding abnormalities and only 1.9% were agreed. Most (95.6%) of respondents agree or strongly agree that it is important for all women to know the correct procedure for BSE.

Table -4

Distribution of Breast Self Examination Practices and Abnormalities Identified

Practice	Frequency	Percent
1.Do you Perform Breast Self Examination		
Yes	86	54.1
No	73	45.9
2.If yes, how often do you perform Breast Self Examination		
Rarely	70	44.0
Every 6 months	12	7.5
Monthly	30	18.9
Never done	47	29.6
3.Have you identified any abnormalities during a Breast Self- Examination		
Yes	7	4.4
No	152	95.6
Total	159	100.0

Among the students, 86 (54.1%) were performing breast self-examination (BSE), while 45.9% did not do BSE. Out of this 18.9% performed BSE every monthly and some had 7.5% performed every 6 monthly. 7(4.4%) had identified some abnormalities while BSE.

Table-5

Distribution of study subjects on Breast Self-Examination Frequency by Family History

12(7.5%) of the students said that having a family history of breast cancer. Out of this only 1(0.6%) were performing BSE monthly. While 11(6.9%) were rarely performing. Most of

How often do you perform Breast Self Examination	Family history		Total	Chi-square	Total
	Yes	No			
Rarely	11 (6.9)	59 (37.1)	70 (44)	12.271	0.007*
Every 6 months	0	12 (7.5)	12 (7.5)		
Monthly	1 (0.6)	29 (18.2)	30 (18.9)		
Never done	0	47 (29.6)	47 (29.6)		
Total	12 (7.5)	147 (92.5)	159 (100)		

students with no family history (18.2%) perform BSE monthly compared to those with a family history.

Table-6

Descriptive statistics on knowledge score about Breast Self-Examination

Knowledge	Mean	SD	Maximum	Minimum
1 st year	4	2.74	0	8
2 nd year	7.58	3.14	0	12
3 rd year	9.26	2.04	5	12
Total	9.1	2.67	12	0

The mean scores increase progressively from 4.00 in the 1st year to 7.58 in the 2nd year, and 9.26 in the 3rd year, reflecting an overall improvement in knowledge levels. The maximum score of 12 was achieved in both the 2nd and 3rd years.

Table-7

Descriptive statistics on Attitude score about Breast Self-Examination

Attitude	Mean	SD	Maximum	Minimum
1 st year	4.09	2.61	8	0
2 nd year	4.17	2.56	8	0
3 rd year	4	2.74	8	0
Total	4.09	2.67	8	0

The mean scores are very similar across the years (ranging between 4.00 and 4.17), showing that students across all three years have, on average, similar attitudes.

Table-8

Correlations between Knowledge Levels cross the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd years of study.

Year of study		1 st year Knowledge	2 nd year Knowledge	3 rd year Knowledge
1 st year Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.368**	-.119
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.008	.411
	N	50	50	50
2 nd year Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	.368**	1	-.040
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008		.776
	N	50	56	53
3 rd year Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	-.119	-.040	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.411	.776	
	N	50	53	53

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

1st Year Knowledge shows a statistically significant positive correlation with 2nd Year Knowledge ($r = .368, p = .008$), suggesting that 2nd years had more knowledge regarding BSE as compared to 1st year students. No significant correlations were found between 2nd Year Knowledge and 3rd Year Knowledge ($r = -.040, p = .776$).

Table-9

Correlations between Knowledge Levels cross the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd years of study.

Year of study		1 st year Attitude	2 nd year Attitude	3 rd year Attitude
1st year Attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	.305*	-.133
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.026	.356
	N	53	53	50
2nd year Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.305*	1	.128
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.026		.377
	N	53	56	50
3rd year Attitude	Pearson Correlation	-.133	.128	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.356	.377	
	N	50	50	50

Year*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

2nd year Shows a moderate positive correlation with 1st Year Attitude. Showing significant ($r = .305, p = .026$).

Discussion:

In the current study, the majority of students (96.2%) recognized that BSE is an effective tool for the early identification of breast carcinoma. Additionally, 84.9% understood that BSE should be performed monthly, a knowledge rate comparable to other studies. For example, the study conducted at Damascus University reported that 89.6% of female students were aware of BSE, and 55.7% had performed it at least once, showing a higher level of practical engagement compared to the 54.1% of students in the current study who reported performing BSE. However, similar to the findings in this study, many students lacked knowledge regarding the specific techniques involved in performing BSE. Only 60.4% of participants in the present study knew that BSE should be performed using the pads of the middle three fingers in circular motions, and 37.7% were unsure. This is in line with findings from the study by Alshafie at Damascus University, where knowledge about specific BSE techniques was not universal, even though 89.6% had heard of BSE. The gap in practical knowledge highlights the need for more comprehensive training in BSE techniques as part of educational programs⁽¹¹⁾.

Attitude Toward BSE

The attitudes of the study participants in the current study toward BSE were largely positive. A significant majority (95.6%) agreed or strongly agreed that it is important for all women to know the correct procedure for BSE, with only 1.3% strongly disagreeing. This is consistent with findings in other studies, such as the one by Tomic et al., which emphasized that female medical students, although knowledgeable, had mixed levels of practical engagement with BSE due to lack of confidence or fear of finding abnormalities⁽¹²⁾. In this study, the majority of students (79.3%) disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement that they avoided BSE because they were worried about finding abnormalities. This suggests that, unlike students in the study by Doshi et al., who reported significant fear related to performing BSE, Saudi female medical students demonstrated more positive attitudes and less apprehension about performing BSE⁽²⁾. This could be attributed to the higher levels of knowledge and educational exposure they receive, particularly in medical school.

Practice of BSE

Regarding the practice of BSE, 54.1% of participants in this study reported performing BSE, with the majority of them doing so infrequently (44%) or only on a rare basis. A similar pattern was seen in the study by Doshi et al., where female dental students showed a relatively low level of engagement with BSE despite a good attitude and awareness of its importance. In contrast, the study by Alshafie reported that a larger proportion of medical students (55.7%) had performed BSE at least once⁽¹¹⁾. The discrepancy between knowledge, attitude, and practice of BSE suggests that while students acknowledge its importance, they may lack the practical motivation or the time to regularly perform BSE. This could be due to the academic pressures faced by medical students, which may limit their ability to engage in self-care practices such as BSE.

Additionally, the present study found that a small percentage (4.4%) of students identified abnormalities during BSE, suggesting that either the students were not performing the examination thoroughly, or they had limited experience in identifying abnormalities. This finding aligns with results from the review by Tomic et al., which highlighted that although medical students understand the importance of early cancer detection, the practical application of this knowledge, particularly in performing BSE, remains limited⁽¹²⁾.

Impact of Family History on BSE Practices

The present study also explored the relationship between family history of breast cancer and the frequency of BSE practice. It was found that only a small percentage of students with a family history (7.5%) performed BSE regularly, with most of them performing it rarely. This is an interesting finding, as one might expect individuals with a family history of breast cancer to be more vigilant about performing BSE. However, this was not the case, as 29.6% of students without a family history of breast cancer reported never performing BSE, which suggests that general awareness and education might be more influential than personal history in determining BSE practices. This is consistent with findings from other studies, such as the one by Tomic et al., which found no significant correlation between family history and BSE practice, suggesting that broader awareness campaigns and education may be more effective than focusing solely on family history as a motivating factor⁽¹²⁾.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, while there is strong awareness and positive attitudes towards breast self-examination (BSE) among female medical students, the practice of BSE is not consistently followed, with only half of the students performing it regularly. Despite good knowledge about its importance for early detection, many students lack practical engagement, likely due to time constraints and insufficient training. The study underscores the need for improved education and training on BSE techniques to ensure better implementation and early breast cancer detection.

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